

THE THEME OF CHILDHOOD IN THE NOVELS OF DORIS LESSING

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Annotation: the article deals with the theme of childhood in Doris Lessing's novel "The Fifth Child".

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The theme of childhood never ceases to sound on the pages of works of world fiction. However, each era makes its own contribution and its own adjustments to the interpretation of understanding the image of childhood.

In the study of the image of childhood in fiction, an important place occupies the concept of an artistic image and its structure. The artistic image is the most complex category of art, which distinguishes it from all other forms of cognition of reality. The image is often understood as the result of the reflection of an object in the mind of a person and, at the same time, the realization of the historical and cultural experience of both individual and social consciousness; it is an element of the artistic whole, which has an independent life and content. In a narrow and more specific sense, the concept of an artistic image denotes an element, a part of a work of art (a character or an object of an image), in a broader and more general sense, a way of being and reproducing a special, artistic, reality, the "realm of visibility".

English children's literature is one of the most significant among European children's literature. Its formation and development is subject to general laws, but there are also specific national features. The formation of a circle of children's reading (works specially intended for children) and literature "adult", selected by the time for children, determines the inseparable connection of children's literature with all the national literature of the English people.

The culture of childhood traditionally attaches great importance to literature for the little ones. The mental characteristics of the age correspond to the system of genres (it is dominated by lyrical and lyrical-epic works) and the general style of children's literature, which consists in the simplicity and accessibility of the text for the perception of children, in the clarity and clarity of thought, in the richness of the word and image. A work for

kids often seems very simple, almost primitive, but this simplicity is the result of the most complex interaction of artistic techniques and means.

The works of English folklore were originally addressed to an adult listener (reader). In the early stages of history, people not only took care of maintaining their existence, but also sought to preserve their tribe, their clan. Everything that contributed to the education of a smart and dexterous person became the content of lullabies, nursery rhymes, riddles, fairy tales. Life experience, accumulated knowledge about the surrounding world, wise conclusions of adults in the form of original teachings were presented to children in simple and understandable forms. The oldest literary monuments: myths, legends, tales - reflect high ideas about Man and his vocation on Earth sound like a true hymn to heroism, reason, nobility, goodness. Thus, myths served as a kind of source for the development of scientific ideas, the birth of philosophy, literature, painting, and theatrical art. The most ancient fairy tales reveal a plot connection with primitive myths, rituals, and customs. Over time, with the development of human society, children "appropriated" most of these fairy tales, myths, legends, as they later "appropriated" many outstanding works of world literature.

The ideal of childhood is refuted most consistently in novel Doris Lessing (1919-2013) *The Fifth Child* (1988), which, according to the author, was created under the influence of the tragic events of the twentieth century. It is dedicated to the history of the breakup of the Lovatt family, like to how "the wars destroyed a beautiful home with all the loving children" of the writer herself. Many years later, she turns to comprehension of the impressions of her childhood, seeing in the public life of the 1970s and 1980s a similar atmosphere destructive for the family, when "some all the time feel a kind of pain, hopelessness, anger" [Rothstein, 1988].

David and Harriet The Lovatts, in defiance of the freedom and looseness of the sixties, decide to devote their lives to creating a strong large large family. Initially, their existence resembles a fairy tale brought to life, so the heroes compare their large Victorian house with a "kingdom", a "fortress". Life in it takes place in accordance with the Christian holiday cycle of alternating Christmas and Easter, in complete isolation from the "greedy and selfish sixties" when "cruelty and crime became commonplace". The idyll is broken by the birth of the fifth child, Ben, whose unusual appearance ("cold

inhuman eyes”, “dense little figure with a large head, yellow stubble of coarse hair”, heavy low forehead” and aggressive behavior towards animals and peers completely contradict the traditional view about the child archetype.

Thanks to comparisons with mythological characters (dwarf, hobbit, troll, goblin), unusual birth circumstances Ben, like Dick, a character in G. Swift's novel, is associated with Jung 's Divine Child. But in contrast to the centuries-old tradition, its appearance does not portend salvation, but, on the contrary, testifies to the wild, dark side of human nature, the absolute overcoming of which is impossible. Ben's inhuman qualities are not the result of degradation, as was the case in previous novels: Lessing insists on his innate cruelty and savagery, which are interpreted as an atavism, a memory of the prehistoric primitive existence of mankind. The complete opposite of Ben are the angelic Paul and Amy , embodying "the faces of good and evil of human nature, like Janus." The appearance of Ben in the ideal Lovatt family based on love (the surname of the characters is formed from English word "love"), indicates the illusory hopes of David and Harriet to hide from the plagues and problems of the civilization in which they live. The paradox is that Ben doesn't seem exceptional to anyone outside of the Lovatt family . There are other children in the school who lack the ability to learn, there are attacks of cruelty, for psychologists and teachers he is just a “hyperactive”, “difficult” child who is not loved by his mother. From this point of view, Lessing's shocking novel is a protest against the British society of the 1980s , which is devoid of clear criteria for humanity, whose ideology is based on a rational perception of the world and an indifferent attitude to morality and spirituality.

The book can be interpreted in different ways. On the one hand, everyone is to blame. The classical family turns into a phantom, where people, as it turned out, are not attached to each other at all. The very first test of sympathy and empathy revealed this illusory nature of family and social ties.

On the other hand, no one is to blame. People - Lessing's favorite thought - are really different. And if, due to the prevailing foundations and circumstances, under normal conditions they stick together, then this connection, as we see, is still fragile. And people like Ben (and how many of them, such Bens, roam among us) are completely

incapable of "equality and brotherhood" in the human anthill. Neither education, nor training, nor even love will help.

The diagnosis is rather ruthless, but accurate. You can read the book like this: the family of David and Harriette at first successfully resists modern "negative" trends, defending the right to tradition and conservatism. But nothing can be changed, and trouble comes from the other side. In the form of, so to speak, traditionalism squared - and the unfortunate family has nothing to oppose to it.

The conclusions of Doris Lessing are cruel and bitter, but in many ways, alas, everything is so. Roads paved with good civilizing intentions have too often led to hell in human history.

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